

A Health Facility-based Analytical cross sectional Assessment of Factors Influencing Birth weight in Kwaebibirem

Brainard Ayisi Asare¹, Grace Asare²

¹Eastern Region, Kwaebibirem, Ghana

²Ghana Health Service, Kade

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559641>

Published Date: 18-May-2022

Abstract: Objective: Birth weight (BW) is associated with increased risk of perinatal mortality when < 2.5kg. Despite the underlying role of a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors of unclear proportionate distribution, reduction of the global burden remains a priority. This study analyses maternal and environmental factors influencing BW.

Methodology: This analytical cross sectional review inferentially compared parturients who delivered singleton babies with BW above or below < 2.5kg across hypothesized risk variables. A total 4,027 singleton live births, from 2015 to 2020 were retrospectively studied.

Results: The overall mean BW was 3.05kg ± 0.4. About 90% of babies weighed 2.5-3.9kg, 5.9% weighed < 2.5kg while 3.8% weighed ≥ 4kg. Adolescent parturients (21.9%) recorded the highest prevalence of BW < 2.5kg. Urban and peri-urban residents recorded a comparatively lower prevalence of BW < 2.5kg. Primiparous parturients recorded a lower mean BW and a commensurately higher prevalence of BW < 2.5kg. Mean Hb concentration was higher among parturients with babies weighing ≥ 2.5kg while mean systolic and diastolic BP were inversely lower among this same category of parturients. Maternal adolescence (POR=2.1, 95% CI=1.2-3.6), rural residence (POR=2.0, 95% CI=1.15-3.5), primiparity (POR=2.4, 95% CI=1.4-4.0), prematurity (POR=8.4, 95% CI=4.7-14.9) and early term (POR=2.4, 95% CI=1.4-4.2) increased risk for BW < 2.5kg.

Conclusion: Efforts to reverse adolescent pregnancy rates, (inextricably linked to high risk for BW < 2.5kg and prematurity), should be enhanced. Research to further investigate mechanisms underlying the role of primiparity, maternal hemoglobin concentration and maternal gestational or chronic hypertension should be prioritized.

Keywords: Birth weight, factors, maternal, environmental.

1. INTRODUCTION

Birth weight (BW), the body weight of a baby at its birth, (varying by mean across various geographical regions), is of medical importance as BW < 2.5kg is associated with increased risk of perinatal mortality.^{1, 2} The prevalence of BW < 2.5kg, (i.e. Low birth weight or LBW), slightly decreased from 7.9% in 1970 to 6.8% in 1980. A slight increase to 8.2% was observed in 2006 and further slightly trended upwards from 2012 to 2019.^{2, 3, 4} Extant evidence has widely investigated factors that likely causally predict BW above or below 2.5kg. Two genetic loci, (i.e. ADCY5 and CCNL1), as well four that show some evidence, (i.e. CDKAL1, HHEX-IDE, GCK, and TCF7L2), have been strongly linked with BW.^{5, 6, 7} The estimated heritability of BW ranges between 25-40 % while complex relationships further exist between a baby's genes and the maternal environment in which the baby develops.^{8, 9} Other important factors linked with BW include maternal health status during pregnancy, environmental factors (e.g. maternal nutrition, smoking and genital infection), among others.^{10, 11, 12, 13}

BW, (also an indicator of the mother and baby's health), is characterized by variations between continents, countries, and cities.¹⁴ Despite estimates indicating ≥ 20 million babies, (or $\geq 16\%$ of all babies globally), are born each year with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$, consistent acquisition of accurate estimates remains difficult. Significant proportions of babies delivered in low income countries are not weighed.¹⁴ LBW country estimates are therefore adjusted to account for underreporting resulting from poor surveillance and questionable data quality in low income countries.¹⁵ South Asia accounted for the highest burden of babies not weighed at birth with 66% and commensurately the highest LBW prevalence at 28% between 2008-2012 while West and Central Africa ranked second with 14%.¹⁵

BW, like growth, is determined by a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors whose proportionate interplay remains unclear.¹⁶ The influence of environmental factors is strongly pronounced by BW variations within genetically similar populations, secular changes and a characteristic reverse social gradient where increasing disadvantage is associated with decreasing BW.¹⁶ The role of maternal stress and exposure to some occupations during pregnancy remains inconclusive while the role of other factors, (e.g. maternal age), though not themselves environmental, are strongly influenced by the social environment.¹⁶

Intrauterine growth and development, (invariably largely assessed by BW in developing countries), constitutes a vulnerable process in the human life cycle whose aberrations bear lasting profound influences in later life.¹⁷ BW therefore comprises a reliable index of intrauterine growth and also a sensitive predictor of survival, growth and long term physical and psychosocial development.¹⁷ LBW babies, (distinctly defined by BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ regardless of gestational age), are 40 times more likely to die within the first four weeks of life than normal weight (or NBW) babies. An estimated 50% of all perinatal and about 34% of all infant mortalities occur among babies with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ while their survival is further associated with significantly high risk for lower IQ and adult onset obesity and diabetes.¹⁸ Reduction of the LBW burden is therefore long recognized as a public health priority that calls for global commitment.¹⁸ Attainment of targets for reduction would positively impact perinatal mortality and expedite progress towards attainment of other nutrition targets, (e.g. reducing stunting, wasting and other forms of malnutrition).¹⁸ While progress in reducing LBW has stagnated since the year 2000 and particularly between 2010-2015, meeting the World Health Assembly's targets for reduction remain a remote reality globally.¹⁸ Interventions targeting LBW reduction therefore call for comprehensive understanding (of the modifiability) of the contextual fetal, maternal, environmental and socio-demographic factors. This study analyses maternal and environmental factors influencing BW.

2. METHODOLOGY

This health facility-based analytical cross sectional study was completed with data on obstetric and newborn care services abstracted from the maternity/labor suit of the Kade Government hospital. The hospital comprises the primary referral health facility in the Kwaebibirem municipality serving an estimated municipal population of 146,346 and an estimated 35, 123 women of fertility age. Five-year data on 4,027 singleton live births covering the years 2015-2020 were abstracted from delivery registers i.e. the registers for mandatory entry of particulars on all institutional births. Parturients who delivered babies with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ were inferentially compared with parturients who delivered babies with BW $\geq 2.5\text{kg}$ across various hypothesized risk variables. Observations were included in the study within the context of a retrospective data review completed through non-probability convenience sampling of available records on singleton births. All multiple deliveries were excluded.

The primary source document for information for the study, the delivery register, was arbitrarily divided into four parts; the first part contains parturients' personal information, (i.e. age, urban/peri-urban or rural community of residence, highest level of education attained and gravidity and parity). The delivery register secondly records information on antenatal clinic-relevant indicators, i.e. maternal hemoglobin (Hb) concentration level, antenatal clinic (ANC) attendance, gestational age at delivery, intermittent preventive therapy with sulfadoxine-pyremethamine (IPTp-SP) doses during pregnancy and maternal ABO phenotypical blood groups. Additionally documented in this part of the register is information on maternal syphilis, hepatitis B and HIV infection status and maternal systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP). HIV information is captured within the programmatic context of 'Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission' (PMTCT) services.

The register thirdly records neonatal information, (i.e. APGARS, fetal heart rate, fetal respiration within 30 minutes, fetal presentation and measures of fetal dimensions). It lastly records information on complications following delivery, (i.e. postpartum hemorrhage, antepartum hemorrhage, obstructed labor etc.). Variables analyzed in this study were mainly

abstracted from the first and second parts of the delivery register coupled with BW information from the third part of the register. BW, the primary measure of interest, (analyzed in two levels independently of GA), was recoded into two mutually exclusive binary outcome variables of $< 2.5\text{kg}$ and $\geq 2.5\text{kg}$; the latter includes $2.5\text{-}3.9\text{kg}$ and $\geq 4\text{kg}$ classified as normal BW or NBW and high BW or HBW respectively.²⁰ Definitions of preterm (i.e. < 37 gestational weeks), early term (i.e. 37-38 gestational weeks), full term (i.e. 39-40 gestational weeks), late term (i.e. 41-42 gestational weeks) and post term (i.e. ≥ 42 gestational weeks) were adopted from specifications of the American College of Gynecologists (ACOG).²¹ Singleton babies delivered at ≤ 28 completed gestational weeks were excluded irrespective of the documented survival status or APGAR scores. Definition of urban/peri-urban and rural communities were consistent with the conveniently used threshold population size for determining localities that can be considered as urban or rural.¹⁹ Based on this convenience, Ghana has over the years defined an urban area to include all localities with $\geq 5,000$ population.¹⁹ Peri-urban communities comprised those adjoining urban areas, i.e. communities or settlements around urban areas whose dynamics varied negligibly from that of the adjoined urban area.

Access to hospital data was granted by the hospital's medical superintendent. All data were analyzed with epi info 3.5.4. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the baseline maternal and new born characteristics. Categorical data are presented in proportions and the differences in maternal, socio-economic and socio-demographic characteristics, (analyzed by BW), were examined using Yates corrected Chi-squared test. Yates corrected Chi-squared value was quoted to avert the risk for biased upwards adjustment of 2×2 contingency tables (associated with Pearson's chi-square and McNemar's test) making results higher than they should be.²² Statistical significance of computed point estimates was interpreted at the conventional significance level of ≤ 0.05 , (i.e. 5% or 1 of 20), at the confidence level of 95%. Where the expected value of a cell was < 5 , Fisher exact test value for significance of the point estimate was used. Prevalence odds ratios (PORs) were analyzed as point estimates of primary interest and not as estimates of risk ratios (RR), odds ratios (OR) or prevalence ratios PR).^{23, 24}

3. RESULTS

BW varied significantly by prevalence among babies delivered 2015-2020. BW of 2.5-3.9kg remained most prevalent at 90.3%. The overall prevalence of babies with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ remained comparatively low at 5.9% while babies with BW $\geq 4\text{kg}$ were observably represented by a lower still prevalence of 3.8%. The mean BW of all babies delivered in Kwaebibirem was $3.05\text{kg} \pm 0.4$. BW was not recorded for about 91 babies i.e. 2.2% of the observations. Parturients aged ≤ 20 years, (the third most prevalent sub population of parturients), accounted for the highest proportion of babies with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$. This observably reduced along the gradient of advancing parturient age above > 20 years. Urban and peri-urban residents recorded a lower prevalence of BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ as compared with rural residents. Parturients, unexposed to formal education together with those exposed to primary school education, (i.e. nil education and ≤ 6 years of formal education), comprised the second largest sub population of parturients. They recorded a comparatively higher prevalence of babies with BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ as compared with those documented to have higher levels of education. The prevalence of BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$ notably decreased along the gradient of increasing parturient level of education with parturients of tertiary educational backgrounds recording the lowest burden. BW did not vary significantly by formal or informal maternal occupation status. Primiparous parturients, the second largest sub population of parturients, recorded a lower mean BW and a commensurately higher prevalence of BW $< 2.5\text{kg}$. This was observably characterized by a steady downward trend in the LBW burden along the gradient of increasing parity. [Table 1]

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of parturients analyzed by birth weight above or below 2.5kg

Characteristic	Characteristic - %	Mean Birth weight - kg	Standard Deviation \pm	Birth weight	
				$<2.5\text{kg}$	$>2.5\text{kg}$
Age					
≤ 20 years	21.9	2.89	0.4	8.9	90.2
21-30 years	46.0	3.06	0.4	5.1	94.9
31-40 years	28.2	3.13	0.4	4.7	95.3
≥ 41 years	3.8	3.16	0.5	2.4	97.6
Area of residence					
Urban	42.6	3.08	0.4	3.8	92.5
Rural	57.7	3.02	0.4	7.5	96.2
Education					
\leq Primary	19.0	3.06	0.4	7.5	92.5

Junior High School	61.5	3.03	0.4	5.9	94.1
Senior High School	14.4	3.06	0.4	5.3	94.7
Tertiary	5.0	3.18	0.3	1.9	98.1
Occupation					
Formal	13.1	3.03	0.4	6.0	94.0
Informal	86.9	3.07	0.4	5.3	94.7
Parity					
Primipara	29.5	2.88	0.4	9.9	90.1
Bipara	19.8	3.04	0.4	5.9	94.1
Multipara	40.9	3.14	0.4	3.7	96.3
Grand multipara	9.9	3.14	0.4	3.9	96.1
Antenatal care					
Yes	81.0	3.06	0.4	5.8	94.2
No	19.0	3.01	0.4	6.6	93.4
Term status					
Preterm (≤ 36 weeks)	9.3	2.67	0.5	27.3	72.7
Early term (37-38 weeks)	25.0	2.93	0.4	11.0	89.0
Full term (39-40 weeks)	47.0	3.12	0.4	1.9	98.1
\geq Late term (≥ 41 weeks)	18.7	3.22	0.4	1.1	98.1
IPTp-SP doses					
Nil dose	3.6	2.98	0.4	11.8	88.2
One dose	22.7	3.02	0.4	7.6	92.4
Two doses	34.5	2.99	0.4	6.4	93.6
Three doses	26.4	3.18	0.5	3.4	96.6
\geq Four doses	12.7	3.23	0.4	1.7	98.3
Anemia status					
Yes	71.2	3.07	0.4	5.6	94.4
No	28.8	3.08	0.4	8.6	91.4
Severity of anemia					
Mild	36.5	3.10	0.4	7.2	92.8
Moderate	61.6	3.06	0.4	4.6	95.4
Severe	1.9	2.64	0.5	11.1	88.9
ABO Blood Group					
A	21.9	3.04	0.4	4.7	95.3
AB	3.5	3.23	0.5	7.7	92.3
B	18.1	3.09	0.4	6.9	93.1
O	56.5	3.09	0.4	4.5	95.5
Syphilis					
Positive	3.0	3.23	0.5	3.2	96.8
Negative	94.6	3.05	0.4	6.1	93.9
Not done	2.4	3.04	0.4	0.0	100.0
Hepatitis B					
Positive	4.3	3.05	0.4	4.4	95.6
Negative	92.2	3.05	0.4	6.0	94.0
Not done	2.5	2.95	0.32	0.0	100.0
PMTCT					
Positive	1.9	2.90	0.2	0.0	100
Negative	96.9	3.05	0.4	6.3	93.7
Not done	1.2	3.17	0.4	0.0	100
Sex					
Male	52.4	3.09	0.4	5.7	94.3
Female	47.6	2.99	0.4	6.1	93.9

Despite a wide standard deviation of $SD \pm 7.4$ and variance, mean maternal age remained comparatively lower among parturients who delivered babies with $BW < 2.5\text{kg}$. Mean parity was marginally lower among parturients who delivered babies with $BW < 2.5\text{kg}$. Mean ANC, IPTp-SP and gestational age, (all conceivably interlinked variables), remained comparatively higher among parturients who delivered babies with $BW \geq 2.5\text{kg}$. While mean Hb concentration was observably higher among parturients who delivered babies with $BW \geq 2.5\text{kg}$, mean systolic and diastolic BP were inversely lower among this same category of parturients. Systolic and diastolic maternal BP were characterized by wide $SD \pm$ and variance. [Table 2]

Table 2. Mean parturient characteristics analyzed by delivery of babies above or below 2.5kg

Characteristics	Parturients with babies < 2.5kg N (%)			Parturients with babies ≥ 2.5kg N (%)		
	Mean	Std. deviation ±	Variance	Mean	Std. deviation ±	Variance
Maternal age	24.8	7.4	56.0	27.3	7.0	50.2
Parity	1.2	1.6	2.7	1.8	1.7	3.0
ANC visits	4.5	2.1	5.8	5.8	2.6	6.8
Gestational age	36.3	3.0	9.6	39.1	1.7	3.2
IPTp-SP Doses	1.7	0.9	0.9	2.2	1.1	2.2
Hb concentration	10.2	1.3	1.7	10.4	4.7	22.9
Systolic BP	125.9	25.8	665.6	118.6	17.1	294.5
Diastolic BP	78.6	18.6	345.9	74.9	28.9	836.2

Adolescent parturients were about twice as likely to deliver babies with BW < 2.5kg. This risk decreased with advancing maternal age despite generation of PORs that did not attain statistical significance. Parturients resident in urban or peri-urban communities were significantly less likely to deliver babies with BW < 2.5kg as compared with those documented to be resident in rural communities. Rural residents were about twice as likely to deliver babies with BW < 2.5kg. Point estimates defining associations between parturients' documented level of education and occupations, albeit suggestively protective, were statically insignificant. The increased risk of being significantly over thrice as likely to deliver babies with BW < 2.5kg among primiparous parturients was eliminated by advancing parity i.e. ≥ bipara. Parturients documented to be ≥ multiparous had a significantly reduced risk of delivery of babies with BW < 2.5kg. Babies delivered preterm, (i.e. < 37 completed gestational weeks), together with those delivered early term, (i.e. between 37-38 completed gestational weeks), consistently with hypothesized expectations, had significantly increased risk for BW < 2.5kg. Advanced gestational age at delivery ≥ 39 completed gestational weeks significantly eliminated the risk of BW < 2.5kg. PORs defining associations between BW and exposure to IPTp-SP doses during pregnancy did not attain statistical significance. [Table 3]

Table 3. Assessment of maternal and environmental factors influencing birth weight

Characteristic	Parturients with babies < 2.5kg N (%)		Parturients with babies ≥ 2.5kg N (%)		POR (95% CI)	p-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No		
Maternal age						
≥20 years	23	212	40	788	2.1 (1.2-3.6)	0.007
21-30 years	25	463	38	537	0.7 (0.4-1.2)	0.3
≥31-50 years	15	325	48	675	0.6 (0.6-1.1)	0.19
Area of residence						
Urban residence	17	427	46	577	0.4 (0.2-0.8)	0.02
Rural residence	45	555	18	449	2.0 (1.15-3.5)	0.01
Maternal education						
Nil	4	66	58	915	0.9 (0.3-2.7)	0.8
Primary	11	118	51	863	1.5 (0.7-3.1)	0.2
Junior High School	38	604	24	377	0.9 (0.5-1.6)	0.9
≥ Senior High School	9	193	53	788	0.6 (0.3-1.4)	0.4
Maternal occupation						
Formal occupation	7	109	56	895	1.0 (0.4-2.3)	0.8
Informal occupation	42	765	21	248	0.6 (0.3-1.1)	0.1
Parity						
Primipara	31	282	32	708	2.4 (1.4-4.0)	0.0008
Bipara	12	191	51	799	0.9 (0.5-1.8)	0.9
≥ Multipara	20	517	43	473	0.4 (0.2-0.7)	0.002
Term status						
Preterm (≤ 36 weeks)	24	64	38	857	8.4 (4.7-14.9)	0.0000001
Early term (37-38 weeks)	27	218	35	703	2.4 (1.4-4.2)	0.0008
Full term (39-40 weeks)	9	458	53	463	0.17 (0.08-0.3)	0.000001
≥ Late term (≥ 41 weeks)	2	181	60	740	0.13 (0.03-0.5)	0.002
IPTp-SP doses						
Nil dose	2	15	23	414	2.4 (0.5-11.1)	0.2
One dose	8	97	17	332	1.6 (0.6-3.8)	0.4
Two doses	10	147	15	282	1.2 (0.5-2.9)	0.7
Three doses	4	113	21	316	0.5 (0.1-1.5)	0.3
≥ Four doses	1	57	24	372	0.2 (0.03-2.0)	0.1

Maternal anemia, defined by Hb concentration of $\leq 10.9\text{g/dl}$, was not significantly associated with BW. Further assessment of maternal anemia along the clinical gradient of severity (from mild to severe) also further yielded PORs that did not attain statistical significance. Maternal ABO phenotypical blood groups and syphilis, hepatitis B, PMTCT positive status were not significantly associated with BW. Neonatal male or female sex status did not impact BW. [Table 4]

Table 4. Assessment of maternal and environmental factors influencing neonatal birth weight

Characteristic	Parturients of babies <2.5kg N (%)		Parturients of babies $\geq 2.5\text{kg}$ N (%)		POR (95% CI)	p-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No		
Maternal Anemia						
Yes	26	437	37	567	0.9 (0.5-1.5)	0.8
No	16	168	47	836	1.6 (0.9-3.0)	0.11
Anemia severity						
Mild	12	154	14	280	1.5 (0.7-3.4)	0.3
Moderate	12	272	13	162	0.5 (0.2-1.3)	0.2
Severe	1	8	25	426	2.1 (0.2-17.7)	0.4
Maternal Blood Group						
Group A	8	162	32	583	0.8 (0.4-1.9)	0.9
Group AB	2	24	38	721	1.5 (0.3-6.9)	0.3
Group B	10	135	30	610	1.5 (0.7-3.1)	0.3
Group O	20	424	20	321	0.7 (0.4-1.4)	0.4
Maternal Syphilis						
Positive	1	30	60	939	0.5(0.06-3.8)	0.4
Negative	60	919	1	50	3.2 (0.4-24.0)	0.17
PMTCT						
Positive	0	18	61	923	Undefined	0.31
Negative	61	913	0	28	Undefined	0.16
Sex						
Male	32	525	31	475	0.5 (0.9-1.5)	0.8
Female	32	525	31	475	0.9 (0.5-1.5)	0.8

4. DISCUSSION

Birth weight (BW), the body weight of a baby at its birth, varied by various maternal, socio-economic and socio-demographic variables in Kwaebibirem. This is consistent with established evidence indicating that BW is characterized by variations between continents, countries, cities and communities.¹⁴ While BW, like growth, is determined by a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors, the proportionate interplay of these factors remains unclear.¹⁶ The overall prevalence of LBW babies at 5.9% was significantly lower than the World bank Ghana estimates of 15% in 2004 and 14% in 2016 and also lower than the estimates of the multiple cluster indicator survey country estimates of 10.7%.^{25, 26} Male babies were generally heavier than female babies by 0.4kg, a wider difference than detected by Agorinya A. I. *et al* who reported a male-female BW difference of 0.1kg.²⁷ A study that consistently identified this male-female BW variation posited that paternal BW significantly influences male but not female weight and further suggested the existence of a genetic regulation along the male line.²⁷ Health facility-based LBW estimates of this study remain considerably lower than the 2018 administrative regional estimates of 14.5% in the Upper East region, 7.9% in Dodowa, 9.9% in the Greater Accra region and in Northern region.²⁷ About 91 or 2.2% of babies did not have documented BW in the delivery register. Other corresponding source documents, (i.e. parturients' personal folder, labor summary sheets etc.), were however not traced to ascertain whether these babies were weighed or not. Defining this inconclusive finding to be consistent with the challenge of significant proportions of babies in developing countries not weighed at birth therefore remains difficult.

While BW remained largely normal among parturients aged ≥ 20 years, younger maternal age or adolescence significantly increased the risk of LBW. This risk was eliminated along the gradient of advancing maternal age. Mean maternal age was commensurately lower among parturients who delivered babies with LBW. This finding lends credence to widely established associations between increased risk of LBW among adolescent parturients.²⁷ Adolescent parturients also however notably recorded the highest burden of preterm deliveries likely and conceivably partly underlying their increased LBW risk. While Restrepo-Méndez C. M. *et al* attribute this to possible confounding from individual socioeconomic status (SES), Widiyanto J. *et al* site the associated role of maternal anemia and not only lower age.^{28, 29} Dennis J. A. *et al* reported differential impact of maternal age by race between African Americans, whites and foreign-

and U.S.-born Hispanics. They conclusively posited that LBW disparities by maternal age are a complex product of socioeconomic disadvantage and current social and behavioral factors, such that LBW risk may not operate uniformly by race, ethnicity or maternal age.^{30, 31}

While parturients in the study were largely rural residents, babies of parturients resident in urban and peri-urban communities were generally heavier by mean difference of 0.02kg. This was defined by a significant prevalence difference between urban/peri-urban and rural LBW burdens of 3.7%. While urban and peri-urban residence reduced risk of LBW delivery by 60%, rural residence contrarily increased the risk by 80%. This corroborates with findings of other studies.¹⁷ Kaur S. *et al* attributed this variation to a less sedentary lifestyle and higher participation in household/caregiving activities, sports activities among rural residents and less occupational activity than urban women.³²

Parturients' with ≤ 6 years of formal education and those with nil exposure to formal education accounted for a higher prevalence of LBW babies. This burden decreased along a gradient of advancing years of exposure to formal education. The LBW burden was therefore comparatively lower among parturients with ≥ 9 years of exposure to formal education. Despite this observed inverse relationship between declining prevalence of LBW with increasing level of formal education, the associated PORs did not attain statistical significance. These findings were inconsistent with otherwise widely established associations between BW and individual SES operationalized as maternal education and dichotomized at various levels.^{33, 34, 35} Studies that have identified significant associations, contrarily to this study, however posit that the underlying mechanism(s) to the association between BW and formal education remain unclear.^{34, 35}

BW varied insignificantly by maternal occupation type dichotomized as formal and informal (i.e. 'white' and 'blue' color jobs respectively). A strong majority of parturients had informal occupations. Other studies, using specific occupations, have reported varied and inconsistent findings that suggest electrical work, metal work etc. significantly influence BW.^{36, 37, 38} Efforts to investigate the influence of maternal occupations have sometimes modeled occupation and education as measures of individual SES. Mean BW, lowest among primiparous parturients at 2.88 ± 0.4 , increased with advancing parity while the LBW burden inversely decreased with advancing parity. Primiparous parturients were over twice as likely to deliver babies with LBW. This was strongly consistent with findings of extant evidence that identify primiparous parturients as a significantly high risk category for delivery of LBW babies.^{39, 40 41, 42} Noteworthy however is the fact that primiparous parturients had a significant composition of adolescents hence also a comparatively higher burden of preterm deliveries.

Though largely attendant, parturients' absolute number of ANC attendances varied significantly i.e. 1-15 attendances. The LBW burden among non-ANC attendants remained marginally higher as compared with that of ANC attendants characterized by a mean difference of 0.05kg. Mean ANC attendance was therefore notably higher among parturients with NBW babies as compared with those who delivered LBW babies i.e. 5.8 ± 2.6 and 4.5 ± 2.1 respectively. This is likely attributable to, (however not invariably), the inextricable links between higher gestational age, higher fetal term status and higher absolute ANC attendances among parturients with heavier babies. These findings lend credence to Zhou H. *et al* who reported increased risk for LBW among women with ≤ 5 ANC visits, non-ANC attendance during the first trimester and lack of access to certain ANC content (e.g. weight, blood pressure, blood test, urine test, ultrasonography and folic acid supplement).⁴³ Metgud S. C. *et al* implicated late ANC registration as a risk factor LBW while Agorinya A. I. *et al* conclusively pointed to an inherent capacity for only effective and adequate ANC to identify LBW risk factors.^{17, 27} This association however remains widely established.²⁸

Findings strongly further corroborated with established associations in extant literature between shorter gestation and LBW infant delivery. Most deliveries occurred at full term (47%) followed by early term (25%), late term (18%) and preterm (9.3%) respectively. Preterm deliveries, characterized by mean BW of 2.6 ± 0.5 , mostly occurred among parturients ≤ 20 years of age at 12.8%. This burden steadily decreased to 8.7%, 7.9% and 5.1% among parturients aged 21-30, 31-40 and ≥ 41 years respectively. The high prevalence of LBW among parturients aged ≤ 20 years in this study, decreased steadily on a gradient of advancing maternal age. Hel V. *et al* however contrarily posit that increase in the LBW burden is seemingly driven by reduced fetal growth rate rather than shorter gestation.⁴⁴

IPTp-SP, a policy-prescribed timeous and effective management of malaria during pregnancy, is widely practiced in malaria endemic parts of the world.⁴⁵ Exposure to IPTp-SP during pregnancy, (despite the observed inverse steady decrease in the LBW burden with increasing doses), did not attain statistical significance. Mean IPTp-SP doses among parturients who delivered babies with BW < 2.5 kg was 1.7 ± 0.9 as compared with 2.2 ± 1.1 among those who delivered

babies with BW ≥ 2.5 kg. As with ANC attendance and BW, while this relationship may remotely be causal, higher IPTp-SP doses are notably and inextricably linked with more advanced gestation and fetal weight in turn. The WHO global malaria program however strongly posits that IPTp-SP prevents the adverse consequences of malaria on maternal and fetal outcomes such as placental infection, clinical malaria, maternal anemia, fetal anemia, LBW and perinatal mortality.⁴⁵

While maternal anemia, (consistent with maternal Hb concentration of < 11.0 g/dl), did not impact BW, descriptive assessment along the clinical gradient of severity pointed to a higher LBW burden among parturients documented to have had severe anemia. Parturients who delivered babies with LBW further had a lower mean maternal Hb concentration of 10.2 g/dl ± 1.3 as compared with 10.4 g/dl ± 4.7 among those who delivered babies with NBW and HBW. This association however did not attain statistical significance. Assessment of duration and trimester of detection of maternal anemia was beyond the scope of this study. Extant literature point to considerable increase in maternal and fetal iron needs during pregnancy leading to established increased risk for LBW delivery when unmet.⁴⁶

Findings indicating insignificant associations between maternal ABO phenotypical blood groups and BW corroborated with Beyazit F. *et al* and Phaloprakarn C. *et al* who also identified insignificant associations.^{47, 48} Further research on much larger samples however remain relevant as Kothari K. L. *et al* identified babies' blood group AB significantly showing a tendency for the lowest BW despite their comparatively lower prevalence.⁴⁹ A homolateral finding in this study also pointed to higher burdens of LBW babies among parturients with AB blood group who coincidentally comprised a significant minority. The prevalence of syphilis among ANC attendants remained low at 3% (despite near universal screening coverage) and did not statistically impact BW. Contrarily however, increased risk of LBW with maternal syphilis remains established in extant literature.^{50, 51, 52} Consistent with findings of Mbangiwa. T *et al*, maternal hepatitis B positive status did not statistically influence BW.⁵³ HIV prevalence of 1.9% among parturients was slightly higher than the national adult estimates of 1.7%.⁵⁴ Contrary to established evidence, maternal HIV positive status in this study did not influence BW.^{55, 56} Parallel documents indicating antiretroviral and compliance statuses of HIV positive parturients and duration of infection were not sought. While the sex of a baby only weakly influenced BW in this study, other studies have identified significantly increased risk of LBW among female babies.⁵⁷ Mean systolic and diastolic maternal BP among parturients who delivered babies with LBW (i.e. 125.9 mmHg ± 25.8 and 78 mmHg ± 18.6 respectively) were higher as compared with those who delivered babies with NBW or HBW (i.e. 118.6 mmHg ± 17.1 and 74.9 mmHg ± 28.9 respectively). While this remains consistent with current evidence, research to distinctly investigate associations between BW and both gestational and chronic (or essential) hypertension should remain a priority.

5. CONCLUSION

The prevalence of NBW, HBW and LBW varied significantly with NBW being most prevalent at 90.3%. The overall prevalence of LBW remained comparatively low at 5.9% while HBW was lower still at 3.8%. Overall mean BW was 3.05 kg ± 0.4 . LBW deliveries mostly occurred among parturients aged ≤ 20 years, a sub population also with significantly increased risk for preterm deliveries. While babies of urban and peri-urban residents were generally heavier and less likely to have LBW, babies of rural residents were significantly likely to have LBW. Exposure to formal education of ≥ 9 years was weakly linked to reduced LBW burdens. Primiparous parturients, twice as likely to deliver babies with LBW, recorded the lowest mean BW at 2.88 ± 0.4 . This characteristically lower BW decreased with advancing parity. ANC attendants and parturients exposed to IPTp-SP during pregnancy generally delivered heavier babies, a finding that calls for further investigation. Maternal anemia, (irrespective of the clinical spectrum of severity), positive maternal syphilis, hepatitis B and HIV status and maternal ABO phenotypical blood groups did not influence BW. Mean systolic and diastolic maternal BP remained higher among parturients who delivered NBW and HBW babies.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Maternal age ≤ 20 years, particularly associated with increased risk of LBW and preterm delivery, comprises a modifiable factor that should be ameliorated to reduce the municipality's high adolescent pregnancy of 21.9%. Multi-sectorial efforts aimed to improve adolescent health and welfare, (e.g. contraception, sustained free and compulsory senior high school education and improved access to information on sexuality, gender-responsive sexual and reproductive health services), should be enhanced and prioritized. Investigation for distinct modifiable factors underlying increased risk of LBW among rural residents will yield comprehensive information for intervention. The positive influence of exposure to formal education of ≥ 9 years on BW should be further researched with larger samples. Research should also further seek to identify specific causal factors predicting increased risk of LBW among primiparous parturients while controlling for the

possible role of adolescent pregnancy. Efforts to increase coverage for IPTp-SP should be enhanced as its link to decreased LBW burden may be associated with its capacity for prevention of malaria and anemia, (both comprising established LBW risk factors). ANC's logistic and human resource capacity for timeous detection of elevated maternal BP, (somewhat a modifiable risk factor), should be assessed and duly strengthened. This would facilitate early, effective and appropriate attention to avert its influence on BW. Continued research to distinctly investigate the influence of both gestational and essential/chronic maternal Hypertension on BW should be prioritized.

REFERENCES

- [1] Georgia Department of Public Health (2008). "Birth weight: Infant's weight recorded at the time of birth", Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Birth_weight, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [2] Yokoyama Y, Jelenkovic A, Hur YM, Sund R, Fagnani C, Stazi MA, Brescianini S. *et al.* "Genetic and environmental factors affecting birth size variation; a pooled individual-based analysis of secular trends and global geographical differences using 26 twin cohorts", *Int Journal of Epidemiology*, 2018, 1; 47(4):1195-1206, DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyy081. PMID: 29788280; PMCID: PMC6124623
- [3] Reduced Incidence of Low Birth Weight, National Collaborative for Infants and Toddlers, Available from: <https://www.thencit.org/measure-impact/select-metrics-for-success/reduced-incidence-of-low-birth-weight>, [Retrieved November 2020]
- [4] de Wilde, JA, van Buuren S, Middelkoop BJ. "Trends in birth weight and the prevalence of low birth weight and small-for-gestational-age in Surinamese South Asian babies since 1974: cross-sectional study of three birth cohorts", *BMC Public Health*, 13, 931 (2013). [https:// DOI.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-931](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-931)
- [5] Yaghootkar H, Freathy RM. "Genetic origins of low birth weight", *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition & Metabolic Care*, 2012 May; 15 (3):258-64, DOI: 10.1097/MCO.0b013e328351f543 PMID: 22406741
- [6] Vasan SK, Neville MJ, Antonisamy B, Samuel P, Fall CH, Geethanjali FS, Thomas N, Raghupathy P, Brismar K, Karpe F. "Absence of birth-weight lowering effect of ADCY5 and near CCNL, but association of impaired glucose-insulin homeostasis with ADCY5 in Asian Indians", *PLoS One*, 2011; 6 (6):e21331, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0021331. Epub 2011 Jun 21, PMID: 21712988; PMCID: PMC3119677
- [7] Ryckman KK, Feenstra B, Shaffer JR, Bream EN, Geller F, Feingold E, et al. (January 2012). "Replication of a genome-wide association study of birth weight in preterm neonates". *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 160 (1): 19–24.e4. DOI:10.1016/j.jpeds.2011.07.038. PMC 3237813. PMID 21885063
- [8] Clausson B, Lichtenstein P, Cnattingius S (March 2000). "Genetic influence on birth weight and gestational length determined by studies in offspring of twins", *BJOG*, 2016, 107 (3): 375–81. DOI:10.1111/j.1471-0528.2000.tb13234.x. PMID 10740335
- [9] Lunde A, Melve KK, Gjessing HK, Skjaerven R, Irgens LM (April 2007). "Genetic and environmental influences on birth weight, birth length, head circumference, and gestational age by use of population-based parent-offspring data", *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 165 (7): 734–41, DOI:10.1093/aje/kwk107, PMID 17311798
- [10] Hedegaard M, Henriksen TB, Secher NJ, Hatch MC, Sabroe S. Do stressful life events affect duration of gestation and risk of preterm delivery? *Epidemiology*, 1996 Jul; 7(4):339-45. doi: 10.1097/00001648-199607000-00001. PMID: 8793357
- [11] Zhu P, Tao F, Hao J, Sun Y, Jiang X. "Prenatal life events stress: implications for preterm birth and infant birth weight", *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, 2010 Jul; 203(1):34.e1-8. DOI: 10.1016/j.ajog.2010.02.023. Epub 2010 Apr 24. PMID: 20417475
- [12] Witt WP, Cheng ER, Wisk LE, Litzelman K, Chatterjee D, Mandell K, Wakeel F. "Maternal stressful life events prior to conception and the impact on infant birth weight in the United States". *American Journal of Public Health*, Feb, 2014, 104 Suppl 1 (1): S81-9. DOI:10.2105/AJPH.2013.301544. PMC 3975462, PMID 24354829
- [13] Khashan AS, McNamee R, Abel KM, Mortensen PB, Kenny LC, Pedersen MG, et al. "Rates of preterm birth following antenatal maternal exposure to severe life events: a population-based cohort study", *Human Reproduction*. February 2009) 24 (2): 429–37. DOI:10.1093/humrep/den418, PMID 19054778

- [14] Low Birth Weight, Country, Regional and Global Estimates, World Health Organization, UNICEF, Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/43184/9280638327.pdf;sequence=1>, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [15] Global Nutrition Targets 2025: Low birth weight policy brief". World Health Organization, Available from: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/149020/WHO_NMH_NHD_14.5_eng.pdf?ua=1, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [16] Nkansah-Amankra S, Luchok KJ, Hussey JR, Watkins K, Liu X. "Effects of maternal stress on low birth weight and preterm birth outcomes across neighborhoods of South Carolina, 2000-2003, *Matern Child Health J*, 2010 Mar; 14(2):215-26. DOI: 10.1007/s10995-009-0447-4. Epub 2009 Jan 28. PMID: 19184386
- [17] Metgud CS, Naik VA, Mallapur MD. Factors affecting birth weight of a newborn--a community based study in rural Karnataka, India. *Plos one*. 2012; 7(7):e40040. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0040040
- [18] UNICEF-WHO Low Birth weight Estimates Levels and trends 2000–2015, Available from: <file:///C:/Users/DR.%20Asare/Desktop/Researches/3.%20Baby%20Studies/2.%20Analytic/Litearture%20for%20the%20write%20up/18.%20WHO-NMH-NHD-19.21-eng.pdf>, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [19] Population and Housing Census Report, 2010, Available from: <file:///C:/Users/DR.%20Asare/Desktop/Researches/3.%20Baby%20Studies/2.%20Analytic/Litearture%20for%20the%20write%20up/19.%20Urbanisation%20in%20Ghana.pdf>, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [20] Birth Weight, Embryology - 8 Mar 2021, Available from: https://embryology.med.unsw.edu.au/embryology/index.php/Birth_Weight, [Retrieved November, 2020]
- [21] Beukelman T, Brunners HI. "Design, Measurement, and Analysis of Clinical Investigations", Textbook of Pediatric Rheumatology (Seventh Edition), 2016, Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/chi-square-test>, [Retrieved in November, 2021]
- [22] Tamhane AR, Westfall AO, Burkholder GA, Cutter GR. "Prevalence odds ratio versus prevalence ratio; choice comes with consequences", *Stat Med*, 2016 Dec 30; 35(30):5730-5735. Doi: 10.1002/sim.7059, Epub 2016 Jul 26, Erratum in: *Stat Med*. 2017 Oct 15; 36(23):3760. PMID: 27460748; PMCID: PMC5135596
- [23] Zocchetti C, Consonni D, Bertazzi PA. "Relationship between prevalence rate ratios and odds ratios in cross-sectional studies", *International Journal of Epidemiology*, Volume 26, Issue 1, Feb 1997, Pages 220–223, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/26.1.220>
- [24] Ghana Fertility Rate 1950-2021, Ghana - Low-birth weight Babies (% of Births), The World Bank, Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.STA.BRTW.ZS>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [25] Ghana Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey with an enhanced Malaria Module and Biomarker, 2011, Ghana Statistical Service, Available from: <file:///C:/Users/DR.%20Asare/Desktop/Researches/3.%20Baby%20Studies/2.%20Analytic/Litearture%20for%20the%20write%20up/26.%20FR262.pdf>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [26] Agorinya IA, Kanmiki EW, Nonterah EA, Tediosi F, Akazili J, Welaga P, Azongo D, Oduro AR. "Socio-demographic determinants of low birth weight; Evidence from the Kassena-Nankana districts of the Upper East Region of Ghana, *Plos one*, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0206207>
- [27] Restrepo-Méndez MC, Lawlor DA, Horta BL *et al*. "The association of maternal age with birthweight and gestational age; a cross-cohort comparison, *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology*, 2015 Jan; 29(1):31-40. DOI: 10.1111/ppe.12162
- [28] Widiyanto J, Lismawati G. "Maternal age and anemia are risk factors of low birth weight of newborn", *Enfermería Clínica*, Volume 29, Supplement 1, March 2019, Pages 94-97, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enfcli.2018.11.010>
- [29] Jeff A. Dennis & Stefanie Mollborn (2013). "Young maternal age and low birth weight risk; An exploration of racial/ethnic disparities in the birth outcomes of mothers in the United States, *The Social Science Journal*, 50:4, 625-634, DOI: 10.1016/j.soscij.2013.09.008
- [30] Lee KS, Ferguson RM, Corpuz M, Gartner LM. "Maternal age and incidence of low birth weight at term; A population study, *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, Volume 158, Issue 1, January 1988, Pages 84-89, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378\(88\)90783-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378(88)90783-1)

- [31] Kaur S, Choon ming Ng, Badon SE *et al.* “Risk factors for low birth weight among rural and urban Malaysian women”, *BMC Public Health*, 19, 539 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-6864-4>
- [32] Gage TB, Fang F, O'Neill E, Dirienzo G. “Maternal education, birth weight, and infant mortality in the United States”, *Demography*, 2013 Apr; 50(2):615-35. Doi: 10.1007/s13524-012-0148-2. PMID: 23073749; PMCID: PMC3578151
- [33] Shmueli A, Cullen MR. “Birth weight, maternal age, and education; new observations from Connecticut and Virginia”, *Yale J Biol Med*, 1999 Jul-Aug; 72(4):245-58. PMID: 10907775; PMCID: PMC2578966
- [34] Chevalier A, O'Sullivan V. “Mother’s Education and Birth Weight”, Available from: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/iza/izadps/dp2640.html>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [35] Sanjose S, Roman E, Beral V. “Low birth weight and preterm delivery, Scotland, 1981-84; effect of parents' occupation”, *Lancet*, 1991 Aug 17; 338(8764):428-31. Doi: 10.1016/0140-6736(91)91045-v. PMID: 1678094
- [36] Farrow A, Shea KM, Little RE. “Birth weight of term infants and maternal occupation in a prospective cohort of pregnant women”, *Occup Environ Med*, 1998 Jan; 55(1):18-23. Doi: 10.1136/oem.55.1.18. PMID: 9536158; PMCID: PMC1757507
- [37] Fenster L, Molly JC. “Birthweight of Infants Born to Hispanic Women Employed in Agriculture”, *Archives of Environmental Health*, Volume 45, 1990 - Issue 1, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00039896.1990.9935924>
- [38] Shah PS; Knowledge Synthesis Group on Determinants of LBW/PT births. “Parity and low birth weight and preterm birth; a systematic review and meta-analyses”, *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scandinavica*, 2010 Jul; 89(7):862-75. Doi: 10.3109/00016349.2010.486827. PMID: 20583931
- [39] Wilcox MA, Chang AMZ, Johnson IR. “The effects of parity on birth weight using successive pregnancies”, *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scandinavica*, 1996
- [40] <https://doi.org/10.3109/00016349609033354>
- [41] Andayasari L, Opitasari C. “Parity and risk of low birth weight infant in full term pregnancy”, *Health Science Journal of Indonesia*, July 2016 7(1) DOI: 10.22435/hsji.v7i1.4701.13-16
- [42] Hinkle SN, Albert PS, Mendola P, Sjaarda LA, Yeung E, Boghossian NS, Laughon SK. “The association between parity and birth weight in a longitudinal consecutive pregnancy cohort”, *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*, 2014 Mar; 28(2):106-15. Doi: 10.1111/ppe.12099. Epub 2013 Dec 9. PMID: 24320682; PMCID: PMC392241543
- [43] Zhou H, Wang A, Huang X, Guo S, Yang Y, Martin K, Tian X, Josephs-Spaulding J, Ma C, Scherpbier RW, Wang Y. “Quality antenatal care protects against low birth weight in 42 poor counties of Western China”, *PLoS One*. 2019 Jan 16; 14(1):e0210393. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0210393. PMID: 30650127; PMCID: PMC6335019
- [44] Eiríksdóttir VH, Ásgeirsdóttir TL, Bjarnadóttir RI, Kaestner R, Cnattingius S, Valdimarsdóttir UA. “Low birth weight, small for gestational age and preterm births before and after the economic collapse in Iceland; a population based cohort study”, *PLoS One*, 2013 Dec 4; 8(12):e80499. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0080499. PMID: 24324602; PMCID: PMC3851132
- [45] WHO Global Malaria Programme. “WHO policy brief for the implementation of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy using sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP)”, Available from: <file:///C:/Users/DR.%20Asare/Desktop/Researches/3.%20Baby%20Studies/2.%20Analytic/Litearture%20for%20the%20write%20up/45.%20ANC%20-%20IPTp-SP.pdf>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [46] Sekhavat L, Davar R, Hosseini-dezoki S. “Relationship between maternal hemoglobin concentration and neonatal birth weight”, *Hematology*, 2011, 16:6, 373-376, DOI: 10.1179/102453311X13085644680186 to link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1179/102453311X13085644680186>
- [47] Beyazit F, Pek E, Güngör AÇ, Gencer M, Unsal MA. “Effect of maternal ABO blood type on birth weight and preeclampsia”, *IJRCOG*, 2017, Vol 6, No 6, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2320-1770.ijrcog20172308>
- [48] Phaloprakarn C, Tangjitgamol S. “Maternal ABO blood group and adverse pregnancy outcomes”, *J Perinatol*, 33, 107–111 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1038/jp.2012.73>

- [49] Kothari LK, Jain TP, Lall KB, Srivastava DK. "ABO blood groups and birth weight", *J Pediatr*, 1969 Sep; 75(3):480-2. Doi: 10.1016/s0022-3476(69)80276-3. PMID: 5804196
- [50] World Health Organization, "Global decrease but cases remain high, causing 200 000 stillbirths and newborn deaths every year", 2019, Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/26-02-2019-who-publishes-new-estimates-on-congenital-syphilis>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [51] Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Sexually Transmitted Infections, Syphilis - CDC Fact Sheet, Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/std/syphilis/stdfact-syphilis.htm>, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [52] Gomez GB, Kamb ML, Newman LM, Mark J, Broutet N, Hawkes SJ. "Untreated maternal syphilis and adverse outcomes of pregnancy; a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2013 Mar 1; 91(3):217-26. Doi: 10.2471/BLT.12.107623. Epub 2013 Jan 17. PMID: 23476094; PMCID: PMC3590617
- [53] Mbangiwa T, Melamu P, Molebatsi K, Anderson M, Bhebhe L *et al*. "Maternal Hepatitis B Virus Infection, Pregnancy, and Infant Health Outcomes in Botswana", *Int Monthly Journal in the Field of Hematology*, Mon. 2019 ; 19(10):e95569. Doi: 10.5812/hepatmon.95569
- [54] List of countries by HIV/AIDS adult prevalence rate, Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_HIV/AIDS_adult_prevalence_rate, [Retrieved January, 2021]
- [55] Taha TE, Dadabhai SS, Rahman MH, Sun J, Kumwenda J, Kumwenda NI. "Trends in birth weight and gestational age for infants born to HIV-infected, antiretroviral treatment-naive women in Malawi", *Pediatr Infect Dis J*, 2012 May; 31(5):481-6. Doi: 10.1097/INF.0b013e31824d9bd9. PMID: 22327871; PMCID: PMC3329585
- [56] Xiao PL, Zhou YB, Chen Y, Yang MX, Song XX, Shi Y, Jiang QW. "Association between maternal HIV infection and low birth weight and prematurity, a meta-analysis of cohort studies", *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, 2015 Oct 8; 15:246. Doi: 10.1186/s12884-015-0684-z. PMID: 26450602; PMCID: PMC4599647
- [57] Mondal B. "Low birth weight in relation to sex of baby, maternal age and parity; a hospital based study on Tangsa tribe from Arunachal Pradesh, *J Indian Med Assoc*, 1998 Dec; 96(12):362-4. PMID: 10489750